

HCR's Inverse Cosine Formula: Solution of internal & external angles of a tetrahedron

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1. Introduction: The Inverse Cosine Formula is a trigonometric relation involving four angular variables and is applicable to any configuration of three straight lines or planes—whether coplanar or non-coplanar—that intersect at a common point in three-dimensional space. The formula establishes a direct relationship between the internal angles of a tetrahedron, defined as the angles between consecutive lateral faces, and the corresponding face angles, defined as the angles between consecutive lateral edges. This relation provides an efficient means of determining all unknown internal angles when the face angles of a tetrahedron are known, and conversely, of computing the face angles when the internal angles are specified. In this paper, a rigorous mathematical derivation of the Inverse Cosine Formula is presented, followed by its application to tetrahedral geometry to demonstrate its validity and computational utility through numerical examples.

2. Axiom of tetrahedron: condition for the existence of any tetrahedron

If α, β & γ are the angles between the consecutive lateral edges meeting at any of the vertices of a tetrahedron then the tetrahedron will exist only and if only the sum of any two angles out of α, β & γ is always greater than third one i.e.

$$(\alpha + \beta) > \gamma, (\beta + \gamma) > \alpha \text{ \& } (\alpha + \gamma) > \beta \quad \forall \alpha, \beta, \gamma > 0 \text{ \& } 0 < (\alpha + \beta + \gamma) < 2\pi$$

3. HCR's Inverse Cosine Formula: It is applicable for any three straight lines or planes, either co-planar or non-coplanar, intersecting each other at a single point in the space.

Statement: If ' α ' is the angle between two concurrent vectors and one of them, keeping other stationary, is rotated (either clockwise or anti-clockwise) by an angle ' β ' about the point of concurrency in a plane inclined at an angle ' θ ' with the plane containing both the vectors in the initial position then the new angle (α') between them in the final (shifted) position is given by the following relation

$$\Rightarrow \alpha' = \cos^{-1}(\cos\alpha\cos\beta + \sin\alpha\sin\beta\cos\theta) \quad \forall (0 \leq \alpha, \theta \leq \pi)$$

The above formula is *Inverse Cosine Formula*.

Proof: Let there be two concurrent vectors \vec{OA} & \vec{OB} inclined at an angle ' α ' and having point of concurrency as 'O'. Now, one of them say vector \vec{OB} be rotated by an angle ' β ' about the point of concurrency 'O' in a plane inclined at an angle ' θ ' with the plane containing both the vectors in initial position & $\angle MON' = \alpha'$ be the angle between the vectors \vec{OA} & \vec{OB}' in the shifted position (as shown in Figure 1).

Now, consider a point 'N' on the rotary vector \vec{OB} and draw the perpendiculars NM & NN' from the point 'N' intersecting fixed vector \vec{OA} & rotated (shifted) vector \vec{OB}' at the points 'M' and 'N'' respectively.

Let $ON = a$, in right $\triangle ONM$

$$\Rightarrow \cos\alpha = \frac{ON}{OM} = \frac{a}{OM} \Rightarrow OM = a \sec\alpha$$

Figure 1: OB' is the final (shifted) position of a rotary vector OB while vector OA is fixed vector

$$\Rightarrow \tan\alpha = \frac{MN}{ON} = \frac{MN}{a} \Rightarrow MN = a \tan\alpha$$

Similarly, in right $\triangle ONN'$ (Fig. 1)

$$\Rightarrow \cos\beta = \frac{ON}{ON'} = \frac{a}{ON'} \Rightarrow ON' = a \sec\beta$$

$$\Rightarrow \tan\beta = \frac{NN'}{ON} = \frac{NN'}{a} \Rightarrow NN' = a \tan\beta$$

Applying Cosine Rule in $\triangle MNN'$ (Fig. 1)

$$\Rightarrow MN'^2 = MN^2 + NN'^2 - 2(MN)(NN')\cos\angle MNN'$$

$$\Rightarrow MN'^2 = (a \tan\alpha)^2 + (a \tan\beta)^2 - 2(a \tan\alpha)(a \tan\beta)\cos\theta$$

$$\Rightarrow MN'^2 = a^2 \tan^2\alpha + a^2 \tan^2\beta - 2a^2 \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta \quad \dots \dots \dots (I)$$

Similarly, applying Cosine Rule in $\triangle MON'$ (Fig. 1)

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \cos\alpha' &= \frac{OM^2 + ON'^2 - MN'^2}{2(OM)(ON')} \\ &= \frac{(a \sec\alpha)^2 + (a \sec\beta)^2 - (a^2 \tan^2\alpha + a^2 \tan^2\beta - 2a^2 \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta)}{2a^2 \sec\alpha \sec\beta} \quad (\text{from Eq(I)}) \\ &= \frac{a^2 \sec^2\alpha + a^2 \sec^2\beta - a^2 \tan^2\alpha - a^2 \tan^2\beta + 2a^2 \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta}{2a^2 \sec\alpha \sec\beta} \\ &= \frac{a^2 (\sec^2\alpha - \tan^2\alpha) + a^2 (\sec^2\beta - \tan^2\beta) + 2a^2 \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta}{2a^2 \sec\alpha \sec\beta} \\ &= \frac{a^2 (1) + a^2 (1) + 2a^2 \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta}{2a^2 \sec\alpha \sec\beta} = \frac{2a^2 + 2a^2 \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta}{2a^2 \sec\alpha \sec\beta} \\ &= \frac{1 + \tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta}{\sec\alpha \sec\beta} = \frac{1}{\sec\alpha \sec\beta} + \frac{\tan\alpha \tan\beta \cos\theta}{\sec\alpha \sec\beta} \\ &= \cos\alpha \cos\beta + \frac{\sin\alpha \sin\beta \cos\theta}{\cos\alpha \cos\beta \sec\alpha \sec\beta} = \cos\alpha \cos\beta + \sin\alpha \sin\beta \cos\theta \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or } \cos\alpha' = \cos\alpha \cos\beta + \sin\alpha \sin\beta \cos\theta$$

$$\Rightarrow \alpha' = \cos^{-1}(\cos\alpha \cos\beta + \sin\alpha \sin\beta \cos\theta) \quad \forall (0 \leq (\alpha, \theta) \leq \pi) \quad \dots \dots \dots (II)$$

The above generalised formula is equally applicable for both coplanar & non-coplanar planes & straight lines intersecting one another at a single point in space. This formula is applied to analyse the three intersecting planes as well as the three intersecting straight lines in the space. With the help of this formula, we can correlate internal angles between the consecutive lateral faces & the face angles between the three lateral edges meeting at any of the vertices of a tetrahedron.

Now, if the angle α' between the vectors in the shifted position is known then the angle of inclination ' θ ' of the **plane of rotation** & the **plane of vectors** in initial position is given by the Eq. (II) as follows

$$\Rightarrow \alpha' = \cos^{-1}(\cos\alpha\cos\beta + \sin\alpha\sin\beta\cos\theta) \text{ or } \cos\alpha' = \cos\alpha\cos\beta + \sin\alpha\sin\beta\cos\theta$$

$$\sin\alpha\sin\beta\cos\theta = \cos\alpha' - \cos\alpha\cos\beta \text{ or } \cos\theta$$

$$= \frac{\cos\alpha' - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}$$

$$\Rightarrow \theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha' - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right) \quad \forall (0 \leq (\alpha, \theta) \leq \pi) \quad \dots \dots \dots (III)$$

The above formula is useful for the solution of a tetrahedron by calculating the correct values of all its internal angles simply by measuring the corresponding face angles (i.e., angle between consecutive lateral edges meeting at any of the vertices of a tetrahedron).

4. Applications of HCR's Inverse Cosine Formula

4.1. Regular tetrahedron: We very well know that each of the faces of a regular tetrahedron is an equilateral triangle. Hence the angle (or face angle) between any two of edges of a regular tetrahedron is 60° hence by setting $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 60^\circ$ in the above formula, we get the internal angle (measured edge-wise) between any two faces of a regular tetrahedron

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 60^\circ - \cos 60^\circ \cos 60^\circ}{\sin 60^\circ \sin 60^\circ}\right) = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2}}{\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}}\right) = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)$$

$$\Rightarrow \theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \approx 70.52877937^\circ \text{ or } 70^\circ 31' 43.6''$$

The above value is the correct value of the angle of inclination between any two faces meeting at any of the edges of a regular tetrahedron, which can be experimentally measured & verified just by cutting it with a plane at the right angle with any of its edges i.e. taking a section normal to any of the edges of a regular tetrahedron.

4.2. Tetrahedron: According to the author, "A tetrahedron is a three-dimensional figure (solid or hollow) completely closed by four non-coplanar planes each three intersecting one another at a single point in the space." These non-coplanar (or generating) planes are called **faces** & the points of intersection are called **vertices** of a tetrahedron. By this definition, it's clear that in any tetrahedron

$$\text{no. of the faces} = \text{no. of the generating planes (always non coplanar)} = 4 \quad \&$$

$$\text{no. of the vertices} = \text{no. of the points of intersection of each three out of four generating planes}$$

$$= \text{no. of ways of selecting three planes out of four} = {}^4C_3 = \frac{4!}{(4-3)!3!} = 4$$

Thus, we can assume any of the four faces of a tetrahedron as the base & rest three as the lateral faces meeting at a certain vertex (see the figure 2 below).

Face Angle: Angle between any two consecutive edges of a tetrahedron is called face angle. The angles α, β & γ are the face angles for the vertex O as shown the Figure 2.

Internal Angle: Angle between any two consecutive faces of a tetrahedron measured from inside. The angles θ_1, θ_2 & θ_3 are the internal angles opposite to the face angles α, β & γ respectively as shown the Figure 2.

Here, we are interested to calculate the all the **internal angles** θ_1, θ_2 & θ_3 (between the consecutive lateral faces meeting at the vertex O) simply by measuring the corresponding **face angles** α, β & γ (i.e. angles between consecutive lateral edges meeting at the vertex O).

4.3. Formula for the internal angles of a tetrahedron: If three planes are intersecting one another at a single point O (such as at the vertex of a tetrahedron) in the space such that the angle between the lines of intersection of the planes are α, β & γ respectively (as shown in Figure 2 below).

This case is similar to the case of the two concurrent vectors i.e. any two lines of intersection of the planes can be treated as two concurrent vectors say OB & OC and third one OA as the rotated vector (see Figure 2).

Hence, using the Eq. (III), all the internal angles between the faces $\Delta OAB, \Delta OBC$ & ΔOAC meeting at the vertex O of a tetrahedron are calculated as follows

1.) The angle θ_1 between the faces ΔOBC ΔOAC is obtained by setting

$\alpha' = \text{face angle to unknown angle } \theta_1' = \alpha$ in Eq. (III),

$$\Rightarrow \theta_1 = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos \alpha - \cos \beta \cos \gamma}{\sin \beta \sin \gamma} \right)$$

2.) The angle θ_2 between the faces ΔOAB ΔOAC is obtained by setting

$\alpha' = \text{face angle opposite to unknown angle } \theta_2' = \beta$ in Eq. (III),

$$\Rightarrow \theta_2 = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos \beta - \cos \alpha \cos \gamma}{\sin \alpha \sin \gamma} \right)$$

3.) The angle θ_3 between the faces ΔOAB ΔOBC is obtained by setting

$\alpha' = \text{face angle opposite to the unknown angle } \theta_3' = \gamma$ in Eq. (III)

$$\Rightarrow \theta_3 = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos \gamma - \cos \alpha \cos \beta}{\sin \alpha \sin \beta} \right) \quad \forall \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 \in (0, \pi)$$

Figure 2: Tetrahedron having faces $\Delta OAB, \Delta OBC, \Delta OAC$ & ΔABC , face angles α, β & γ and internal angles θ_1, θ_2 & θ_3 between the faces

The above formulas are used to find the internal dihedral angles θ_1, θ_2 , & θ_3 of a tetrahedron.

5. Illustrative examples on the application of HCR's Inverse Cosine Formula

5.1. Example 1: Three planes are intersecting each other at a single point in the space such that the angles between two consecutive lines of intersection are $30^\circ, 45^\circ$ & 70° . Find out all the angles between the intersecting planes.

Sol. Let's assume

$$\alpha = 30^\circ, \beta = 45^\circ, \gamma = 70^\circ \text{ \& } \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 = ? \text{ (unknown angles)}$$

Setting the values in HCR's inverse cosine formula, we calculate the values of unknown angles θ_1, θ_2 & θ_3 between the planes successively as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \theta_1 &= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos \alpha - \cos \beta \cos \gamma}{\sin \beta \sin \gamma} \right) \\ &= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos 30^\circ - \cos 45^\circ \cos 70^\circ}{\sin 45^\circ \sin 70^\circ} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{0.866025403 - 0.707106781 \times 0.342020143}{0.707106781 \times 0.93969262}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}(0.939376034) = \mathbf{20.05296774^\circ \text{ or } 20^\circ 3' 10.68''} \\
\Rightarrow \theta_2 &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\alpha\cos\gamma}{\sin\alpha\sin\gamma}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 45^\circ - \cos 30^\circ \cos 70^\circ}{\sin 30^\circ \sin 70^\circ}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{0.707106781 - 0.866025403 \times 0.342020143}{0.5 \times 0.93969262}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}(0.8745597) = \mathbf{29.00709092^\circ \text{ or } 29^\circ 0' 25.53''} \\
\Rightarrow \theta_3 &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 70^\circ - \cos 30^\circ \cos 45^\circ}{\sin 30^\circ \sin 45^\circ}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{0.342020143 - 0.866025403 \times 0.707106781}{0.5 \times 0.707106781}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}(-0.764671757) = \mathbf{139.8777989^\circ \text{ or } 139^\circ 52' 40.08''}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, all the unknown angles are calculated. Since, all the angles between the intersecting planes are less than 180° i. e. $0 < \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 < \pi$ hence all the values are within the range.

5.2. Example 2: The angles between the consecutive lateral edges meeting at a vertex of a tetrahedron are $43.5^\circ, 78.6^\circ$ & 95.2° . Find out all the internal angles between the faces meeting at the same vertex of tetrahedron.

Sol. Let's assume

$$\alpha = 43.5^\circ, \beta = 78.6^\circ, \gamma = 95.2^\circ \text{ \& } \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 = ? \text{ (unknown angles)}$$

Setting the values in HCR's inverse cosine formula, we calculate the values of unknown internal angles θ_1, θ_2 & θ_3 between the consecutive lateral faces successively as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\Rightarrow \theta_1 &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 43.5^\circ - \cos 78.6^\circ \cos 95.2^\circ}{\sin 78.6^\circ \sin 95.2^\circ}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{0.725374371 - 0.19765734 \times (-0.09063258)}{0.980271174 \times 0.995884398}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}(0.761381448) = \mathbf{40.41386481^\circ \text{ or } 40^\circ 24' 49.91''} \\
\Rightarrow \theta_2 &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\alpha\cos\gamma}{\sin\alpha\sin\gamma}\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 78.6^\circ - \cos 43.5^\circ \cos 95.2^\circ}{\sin 43.5^\circ \sin 95.2^\circ}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{0.19765734 - 0.725374371 \times (-0.09063258)}{0.688354575 \times 0.995884398} \right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}(0.38423282) = \mathbf{67.40387892^\circ} \text{ or } \mathbf{67^\circ 24' 13.96''} \\
\Rightarrow \theta_3 &= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta} \right) \\
&= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\cos 95.2^\circ - \cos 43.5^\circ \cos 78.6^\circ}{\sin 43.5^\circ \sin 78.6^\circ} \right) \\
&= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{(-0.09063258) - 0.725374371 \times 0.19765734}{0.688354575 \times 0.980271174} \right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}(-0.346794775) = \mathbf{110.2913941^\circ} \text{ or } \mathbf{110^\circ 17' 29.02''}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, all the unknown internal angles of tetrahedron are calculated. Since, all the internal angles between the faces are less than 180° i.e. $0 < \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3 < \pi$ hence all the values are within the range.

Conclusion: It's obvious from above numerical examples that the inverse formula is the very useful for finding out the

1. Angles between three intersecting planes in the space
2. Angles between three intersecting straight lines in the space
3. Internal angles if the face angles in a tetrahedron are known & vice-versa.
4. Any of the four angles in the formula if rest three are known

Since the external measurement or evaluation of the face angles of a tetrahedron using trigonometric relations is relatively straightforward, whereas the direct measurement of its internal dihedral angles is cumbersome and often requires cutting sections at right angles (90°), which may introduce measurement errors. The proposed formula effectively overcomes this difficulty by enabling the determination of internal angles from externally measurable face angles, thereby improving both the accuracy and precision of the results.

Note: Above articles had been derived & illustrated by Mr H.C. Rajpoot (B Tech, Mechanical Engineering)

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